

Undergraduate Research Project Symposium

Department of Electrical, Electronic and Systems Engineering
Faculty of Engineering and Built Environment
Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia
August 4, 2021

Published by:

Department of Electrical, Electronic and Systems Engineering
Faculty of Engineering and Built Environment
Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia

The publication date: 10th December 2021

Printed in Bangi, Selangor by Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia — 15th December 2021